

Data Repository Selection Matrix for Preclinical Research

- When selecting a data repository, GDPR, AUMC policies, participant anonymization, and requirements from funders and journals need to be considered. The below matrix takes these into account and simplifies this by matching data types to subject types and includes metadata standards to enhance the FAIR principles.
- When multiple repositories are listed, the top-ranked repository must be chosen. In instances where the top-ranked repository is not feasible for any reason, the subsequent repository in the order of preference should be selected.
- When a data type is not listed, publish it at a "General" repository.
- When there are multiple data types or data from multiple samples that need to be published, either publish some data in a data-specific repository and some in a "General" repository or package all data into a single dataset and publish it at a "General" repository.

Table 1. Matrix for preferred data repositories according to data and subject type along with preferred metadata standard

Data Types vs Subject Types/Metadata	Human	Animal	Microbiota	Metadata standards
Genomics <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Genotyping by array • Amplicon sequencing • Genomic variant calling (Variant Calling) 	EGA^{R EU} dbGAP^{R USA}	Array Express^{EU} SRA^{USA} ENA^{EU}	Array Express^{EU} SRA^{USA} ENA^{EU}	
Metagenomics <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 16S rRNA sequencing 	N/A	N/A	ENA^{EU} MGnify^{EU} SRA^{USA} Nucleotide^{USA}	MIMS
Transcriptomics <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transcriptome profiling by high-throughput sequencing (RNA-Seq) • Transcriptome profiling by array (Expression Array) 	EGA^{R EU} dbGAP^{R USA}	Array Express^{EU} SRA^{USA} ENA^{EU}	Array Express^{EU} SRA^{USA} ENA^{EU}	MINSEQE
Epigenomics <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Methylation binding domain sequencing (MBD-Seq) • Methylation profiling by high-throughput sequencing (DNA meth) • Histone modification profiling by high-throughput sequencing (ChIP-Seq) 	EGA^{R EU} dbGAP^{R USA}	Array Express^{EU} SRA^{USA} ENA^{EU}	Array Express^{EU} SRA^{USA} ENA^{EU}	
Functional Genomics <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chromatin accessibility profiling by high-throughput sequencing (ATAC-Seq) • Chip-Seq (ChIP-Seq) 	EGA^{R EU} dbGAP^{R USA}	Array Express^{EU} SRA^{USA} ENA^{EU}	Array Express^{EU} SRA^{USA} ENA^{EU}	
Proteomics <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mass Spectrometry • Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy (NMR) 	PRIDE^{EU}	PRIDE^{EU}	PRIDE^{EU}	MIAPE
Metabolomics <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mass Spectrometry • Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy (NMR) 	Metabo Lights^{EU} Metabolomics^{USA} Workbench^{USA}	Metabo Lights^{EU} Metabolomics^{USA} Workbench^{USA}	Metabo Lights^{EU} Metabolomics^{USA} Workbench^{USA}	MIAPE CIMR

Multi-omics	EGA^{R EU}	BioSamples^{EU}	BioSamples^{EU}	
Non-structural Genetic Variations (<50 bp) • VCF files	EVA^{EU} dbSNP^{USA} ClinVar^{† USA}	EVA^{EU}	N/A	
Structural Genetic Variations (>50 bp)	EVA^{EU} dbVar^{USA} ClinVar^{1 USA}	EVA^{EU}	N/A	
Phenotypes • Samples	BioSamples^{EU} BioSample^{USA}	BioSamples^{EU} BioSample^{USA}	BioSamples^{EU} BioSample^{USA}	
Cellular • Flow Cytometry • CyTOF (Mass Cytometry)	Flow Repository^{USA INT 1 2 3} ImmPort^{USA}	Flow Repository^{USA INT 1 2 3} ImmPort^{USA}	Flow Repository^{USA INT 1 2 3} ImmPort^{USA}	MIFlowCyt²
Microscopy • Light Microscopy • 2D Electron Microscopy	BioImage Archive^{EU}	BioImage Archive^{EU}	BioImage Archive^{EU}	Open Microscopy Environment (OME) model
Microscopy • 3D Electron Microscopy (cryo-EM/cryo-ET) • Multiple modalities (e.g. correlative imaging)	EMPIAR^{EU}	EMPIAR^{EU}	EMPIAR^{EU}	
Microscopy • Electron Microscopy without micrographs or particle stacks	wwPDB OneDep^{EU USA JP}	wwPDB OneDep^{EU USA JP}	wwPDB OneDep^{EU USA JP}	
Microarray	Array Express^{EU}	Array Express^{EU}	Array Express^{EU}	
General	BioStudies^{EU} DataverseNL^{NL} Zenodo^{EU} Mendeley Data^{NL UK} Figshare^{INT}	BioStudies^{EU} DataverseNL^{NL} Zenodo^{EU} Mendeley Data^{NL UK} Figshare^{INT}	BioStudies^{EU} DataverseNL^{NL} Zenodo^{EU} Mendeley Data^{NL UK} Figshare^{INT}	

^R the possibility to publish data with restricted access which is suitable for datasets that has some potential to identify the human subjects

[†] clinically relevant genetic variant data, i.e. data that relates genetic variation(s) with clinical significance values (e.g. pathogenic, benign, etc.)

^{EU} European Union based repository, ^{USA} United States of America based repository, ^{INT} International repository, ^{NL} Netherlands based repository, ^{UK} United Kingdom based repository

Additional Resources

- [Selecting a Data Repository - Library Guides at University of Washington Libraries](#)
- [Data submission | Services | EMBL's European Bioinformatics Institute](#)
- [Generalist Repository Comparison Chart](#)

References

1. Spidlen J, Breuer K, Rosenberg C, Kotecha N, Brinkman RR. FlowRepository: A resource of annotated flow cytometry datasets associated with peer-reviewed publications. *Cytometry Part A* 2012; **81A**: 727–731.
2. Spidlen J, Breuer K, Brinkman R. Preparing a Minimum Information about a Flow Cytometry Experiment (MIFlowCyt) Compliant Manuscript Using the International Society for Advancement of Cytometry (ISAC) FCS File Repository (FlowRepository.org). *Curr Protoc Cytom* 2012;Unit 10.18. Available at <http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/0471142956.cy1018s61/full>. Accessed April 7, 2016.
3. Spidlen, J. and Brinkman, R. R., Use FlowRepository to share your clinical data upon study publication. *Cytometry Part B, Clinical Cytometry*. 2018. **94**, 196–198.